

To make Europe's Earth system models fit for exascale
Deliverable D3.5

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1 Abstract / publishable summary

As the demand for higher resolution and more accurate weather and climate simulations increases, the need for exascale supercomputers becomes more pressing. Modern (exascale) supercomputers increasingly rely on graphics processing units (GPUs) as the major source of compute power. However, the process of porting existing weather and climate modelling codes to these new systems presents new challenges.

As many existing weather and climate modelling codes are designed to run on traditional CPU-based supercomputers, significant efforts are required to port the codes to new supercomputers and efficiently utilize GPUs. The transition can be difficult for researchers and developers who are accustomed to working with traditional CPU-based systems and may not have experience with programming and optimizing GPU code.

Along with the evolution of the hardware, the application of weather and climate models is also evolving. For example, when individual models are used as component models in larger coupled simulations, or when models are used as part of larger workflows to produce forecasts at regular intervals.

The goal of the ESiWACE2 services is to create collaborations between the ESiWACE2 partners consisting of Research Software Engineers, HPC experts, and tool builders, and the weather and climate community of model developing groups and end users of weather and climate models. The goal of these collaborations is to provide guidance, engineering, and advice to support the weather and climate community through the evolution process of both the computing hardware and the evolving usage practices to prepare the weather and climate community for the exascale era.

The ESiWACE2 project has created three services. **Service 1: code portability and refactoring** focused on porting and refactoring weather and climate models to new computing architectures, such as GPUs. **Service 2: Coupling, IO and workflows** focused on optimizing the complex use cases of weather and climate models through the use of community-developed tools for model coupling, parallel I/O, and operational workflows. **Service 3: Weather and climate benchmarking** has continued the development of the HPCW benchmark suite to enable in-depth performance analysis and benchmarking of weather and climate codes.

2 Conclusion & results

By establishing three services to the weather and climate community, the ESiWACE2 project has made an important step towards preparing the weather and climate community to make use of exascale supercomputers when they become available. Through Service 1 and 2, the ESiWACE2 project has enhanced the HPC capacity of the weather and climate community and boosted European weather and climate models to efficiently operate on pre-exascale platforms currently available in Europe. Through Service 3, by extending and future-proofing the HPCW Benchmark suite, ESiWACE2 has strengthened the interaction of the weather and climate community with the European HPC ecosystem and fostered co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres.

For example, within the RegCM Service 1 project, we have ported the full non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM to the GPU using OpenACC, substantially improving the performance of RegCM on the Marconi100 supercomputer. With this effort, we have provided a blueprint as well as identified several future directions to the model developing group on how to further improve and gradually port other components within the model to GPUs.

Within the MicroHH Service 1 project, we have improved the performance of seven GPU kernels within MicroHH using auto-tuning technology to automatically select at runtime the optimal configuration for each combination of grid size, hardware platform, and floating-point precision. An average performance improvement of 60% for single precision and 45% for double precision was measured for these seven GPU kernels. Overall, the runtime of a full MicroHH testcase is reduced by 14%, which will save the research group several months off of planned runs on the Snellius supercomputer next year.

The ESiWACE2 Services have made it clear that it is urgent to prepare the weather and climate community to make use of the upcoming exascale supercomputers. This deliverable summarizes the lessons learned within the execution of the ESiWACE2 Services, which we have grouped into six themes from computer and software architecture to running service projects.

Software architectures of weather and climate models need to adapt to reconcile with the increased hardware complexity and the diminishing fraction of compute power provided by CPUs, through the isolation of computational kernels and the adoption of flexible data layouts. Developer time and effort needs to be dedicated to expand test suites, which have proven crucial when porting models to new architectures. Directive-based programming models, as OpenACC and OpenMP, have the advantage that the code remains in the original language. However, this approach has its limitations as specialization towards CPU or GPU architectures in terms of loop optimizations, data layouts, and tuning parameters are still required to achieve good performance.

We have successfully applied advanced software development tools, for auto-tuning and for preprocessor specialization, to create performance portable implementations, and we foresee that such tools will become fundamental for GPU applications (both in CUDA and OpenACC) to achieve high performance in the coming years. Another promising avenue to be explored further on both CPUs and GPUs is the use of mixed-precision. However, to ensure long-lasting impact of porting efforts, it is essential for model developers to be trained in the skills needed to test and build upon the ported model code. Finally, we will apply the lessons learned within the ESiWACE2 services to create even more effective and impactful service projects within ESiWACE3.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in Section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	✓
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	✓
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	✓
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	✗
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	✓
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	✗
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	✓
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	✓

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable is the last deliverable within Work Package 3: HPC services to prepare the community for the pre-exascale. The work performed by the individual services created by Work Package 3 has been covered in several other deliverables:

Service	Deliverable	Month
Service 1	D3.1 Mid-term assessment of the services	M24
	D3.2 Report on services in portability and refactoring	M46
Service 2	D3.3 Report on services offered on IO, coupling and workflow	M49
Service 3	D3.4 Report on services offered on weather and climate benchmarks	M50

As such, the scope of this deliverable (D3.5) is:

- Report on the two Service 1 projects running in 2022, carried out by the Netherlands eScience center, which were still ongoing by the time Deliverable D3.2 was produced. See Sections 4.1 and 4.2 for the reports on the Service 1 projects on RegCM and MicroHH, respectively.
- Summarize the work done in all three Services (Section 4.3).
- Present the lessons learned from the work performed in the services (Section 4.4.1), leading to the main bottlenecks for Europe's models towards exascale simulations (Section 4.5) and how to address them (see Section 4.6). Future developments are addressed in Section 8.

4.1 RegCM Service 1 project

The current project objective is to port to a GPUs cluster a finite fraction of a Regional Climate model currently coded using a 2D cartesian MPI horizontal decomposition. Target of the porting is the newest dynamical core of the model, with the possibility to accelerate also part of the physical parameterization 1D packages. A clear description of the procedure and tools used can possibly enable the model community to complete the task and port a larger fraction of the code on a GPU cluster, thus permitting a larger and more ambitious scientific objective set to be reached in the upcoming round of regional climate model intercomparison projects. A higher resolution description of the current and future earth climate system are the mission given by the United Nation's World Climate Research Programme to the Coordinated Regional Model Intercomparison Project CORDEX.

4.1.1 RegCM overview

The REGional Climate Model [RegCM] is a state-of-the-art limited area model, developed by the Earth System Physics section of the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) for long-term regional climate simulation. It has been used in numerous regional model inter-comparison projects to produce climate projections for the next century by the process of physical downscaling the output of Global Climate Models as part of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP).

The RegCM system is a community model designed for use by a varied community of scientists in industrialized countries as well as developing nations. It is designed to be a public, open source, user friendly, and portable code that can be applied to any region of the world. The model code written in Fortran is released under GPLv3+ licensing. New model versions are presented to the larger model user community (750+ registered users) in regular scientific workshops organized by the ICTP to showcase new technical and scientific capabilities and permit the evaluation of model sequential improvements in the past 20 years.

The model code version control is maintained using Git and hosted on the public GitHub server.

The latest model development iteration has seen the addition of a non-hydrostatic dynamical core. Coupled with model 1D packages that solve the sub-grid scale physics of convection, water phase change, boundary layer, short and long wave solar and long wave earth radiation interaction, the non-hydrostatic dynamical core enables the model time integration to produce climate scenario simulations. The model has an internal coupling with a surface community land model for atmosphere surface interaction description (CLM4.5).

The original model code, serving as a starting point for the ESiWACE2 Service 1 project, is using a full Cartesian MPI decomposition of the horizontal model grid using an Arakawa-C discretization and a nine point stencil for the weight average flux (WAF) advection scheme.

The model coding using MPI only processes does not permit it to take advantage of accelerators (GPU or otherwise) eventually present on the target computation platform. This is orthogonal to the current procurement trend of the major HPC centres in Europe, which in the current round of new Tier0/1 systems are focused on increasing the raw floating point computational performances by using GPU clusters with accelerators on every node. The RegCM code in the MPI configuration cannot access those computational resources on the GPUs, and thus does not qualify for access on the new systems: this limitation is currently precluding research groups from submitting computing time proposals to an increasingly large fraction of national and international computing centers.

The capability to accelerate the model execution using GPUs will open up the road for the RegCM user community to evaluate future climate extremes over multiple high resolution domains all over the world with a focus on high threat areas for climate change such as the Indo-Gangetic plane, Southern Europe, the Sahel Region and the la Plata basin. The 3km resolution can provide useful information on future extremes in temperature and precipitation, serving as red flag warnings for possible life disruptive changes in spot regions around the globe. Currently this is the target of multiple pilot studies.

The porting of a sizeable part of the code to a GPU cluster will later be used as a blueprint to extend the porting to the whole code-base. The capability to accelerate the code on GPU clusters is mandatory for accessing current and near-future HPC platforms.

Two test cases have been prepared for the development process:

- med22: A low resolution European domain at the 50 km horizontal resolution of the previous intercomparison projects

- a1ps: High resolution at 3km resolution over the Alpine region representative of the future Convection Permitting setting for which the GPU clusters would be the target platform to obtain the level of computation performances that would make the scientific project targets viable.

4.1.2 Initial performance analysis

As is the case with most Earth System Models (ESMs), the RegCM can be run in parallel over multiple compute nodes, and as such the achieved wall-clock time depends upon the resolution and physical parameters of the test case, and the allocated cores for a given cluster. To analyze the performance of this software we use the following procedure:

1. Choose a hardware platform, in our case the JUWELS-Booster machine. This cluster contains 936 dual-socket compute nodes with two AMD EPYC Rome 7402 CPU's, each having 24 cores running at 2.8 GHz. Furthermore, every node has 4 Nvidia A100 GPU cards with 40GB memory each. The nodes are connected by an InfiniBand HDR Dragonfly+ topology network.
2. For the most widely used set of Fortran compilers on the platform (in our case GNU Fortran 10.3, Intel Fortran 2021 and Nvidia's nvfortran 22.3), assess the scaling behaviour of the given test cases.
3. Choose a representative configuration, bound by single-threaded performance, to construct a profile.

This procedure is essential at the start of the service project to assess whether the proposed work is expected to generate impact with regard to the application performance.

RegCM scaling on JUWELS-Booster Porting the code to the JUWELS-Booster platform went fairly easy, no substantial compilation problems or performance issues were encountered. The initial benchmarking on JUWELS-Booster reveals highest performance for the `gfortran` compiler and the slowest executable being produced by `nvfortran`, the latter caused a segmentation fault for the `alps` test case. For each compiler we have used the `-O3` flag, compiled for the native architecture and enabled SSE2 instructions. For inter-process communications, OpenMPI 4.1.2 has been used. The scaling plots in fig. 1 show us that the low-resolution model quickly reaches its scaling limit at 240 cores (4 nodes) whereas the `alps` case scales efficiently to 576 cores (12 nodes), where the GNU-compiled binary achieves 2 simulated years per day. We have not investigated the performance gap between the Nvidia compiler and GNU/Intel.

RegCM performance profile We have selected the 4-node `alps` configurations as a suitable case for profiling RegCM: from the above results it is clearly not yet communication-bound but at the same time has a somewhat representative performance of around 0.5 SYPD. We have used the instrumentation-based profiling tool `gprof` for measurement of the most expensive routines. However in the case of `gfortran`, the extra profiling compiler options seemed to disable some function inlining optimizations, causing the `pfesat` function to completely

Figure 1: Strong scaling plots for the low-resolution med22 test case and realistic alps model.

routine	calls	Percentage GNU	Percentage Intel
mod_moloch: wafone	57600	19.3	30.3
mod_moloch: sound	5760	16.4	19.9
mod_micro: noptom	1920	14.7	20.2

Table 1: Top-3 routines populating the flat performance profile. Subsequent entries are all observed well below 5% of the total runtime.

dominate the profile. We have therefore used the Linux builtin sampling-based `perf` tool to obtain an indication of the profile. In all cases, the profile is dominated by the advection routine `wafone`, the sound wave filtering `sound` and the cloud microphysics scheme `noptom` (see tab. 1). The top-10 of most expensive functions was also populated with MPI communications and other `mo1och` module routines.

Based upon these measurements, it was decided to begin the effort with porting the non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM to GPUs using OpenACC. At a later stage, the focus would shift towards the physical parameterizations, with the radiation and cloud microphysics as obvious candidates for GPU acceleration.

4.1.3 Performance improvements

Porting strategy The initial stage of the development work was limited to a *naive port* of the RegCM dynamical core with OpenACC; by this we mean (i) inserting (unstructured) data regions to create GPU arrays necessary to run the ported `mo1och` loops over, (ii) inserting minimal data update clauses to synchronize host-device arrays and vice versa and (iii) annotate loops with parallel regions. The strategy to ensure correctness was to start with a region that is fully GPU-resident and expand this section gradually, using the `med22` test case to measure performance and monitor the output of the model.

Note that this strategy only optimizes at the level of *data movement*: since the `mo1och` time step contains many small and fast loops it was essential to avoid redundant device-host transfers between these, which is the idea behind the 'expanding region' strategy. The simple small 3D-loops are annotated with a collapse clause to give `nvfortran` the liberty to choose an optimized parallel layout for the underlying architecture, e.g.

```
!$acc parallel loop present(p,pai,qsat,t) collapse(3)
do k = 1 , kz
  do i = ice1 , ice2
    do j = jce1 , jce2
      p(j,i,k) = (pai(j,i,k)**cpovr) * p00
      qsat(j,i,k) = pfwsat(t(j,i,k),p(j,i,k))
    end do
  end do
end do
```

```
    end do
end do
!$acc end parallel
```

Increased Parallelism Unfortunately, some loops have appeared more difficult to offload efficiently. Especially in `wafone`, the vertical, meridional and zonal advection loops were originally CPU-optimized in a way that prevents a full parallel layout of the three-dimensional stencil operation. To minimize redundant computations, certain two-dimensional array slices were cached for re-use, introducing a barrier in the inner loop. As a result, the naive OpenACC strategy would yield a very low GPU utilization and a runtime that is more than 20 times slower than the CPU counterpart.

We have introduced algorithmic changes to the above advection loops in the git branch `acc_dycore`, replacing 2d-array caches with redundant computation of neighbouring grid cell fluxes. This resulted in a speedup of the GPU-offloaded advection by 2-3 orders of magnitude, but would also result in a regression of the CPU execution performance, as will be pointed out below.

GPU-aware MPI Both the `wafone` and `sound` routines contain numerous halo exchanges between neighboring partitions. These MPI communications are wrapped in convenience methods that fill a temporary buffer to avoid network congestion. In a first effort, we have enclosed these wrapper methods between device-to-host and host-to-device copying clauses. This introduces a substantial amount of PCI-e traffic that can be avoided. We have ported the wrapper routines to the GPU and leveraged CUDA-aware MPI by using the `host_data use_device(...)` clauses around the MPI point-to-point communications.

However, since the wrappers are being used in other routines in RegCM as well, we have defined a flag, `on_device`, that serves as a condition for the GPU-aware MPI calls, e.g.

```
!$acc host_data use_device(rv2) if(on_device)
call mpi_irecv(rv2, isize, mpi_real8, icpu, tag1, comm, rrq, mpierr)
!$acc end host_data
```

The flag `on_device` is set within the accelerated code region to ensure the original working of the exchanges outside the dynamical core.

Asynchronous data transfers As the accelerated region has expanded to the entire dynamical core, the situation arises where the CPU-resident routines are becoming the exception rather than the rule. Some methods however are not suitable to transfer to the GPU, such as output writing, reading boundary conditions and the physics parameterizations. These functions have been enclosed with device-host synchronization clauses. To mitigate the performance penalty induced by these transfers, we have constructed a separate asynchronous stream for data transfers; this allows us to overlap some data transfers with independent kernel executions.

Porting cloud microphysics scheme The expensive `nogtom` scheme (see table 1) has been ported to OpenACC as a first step towards making the physics parametrization packages device-resident. This scheme is fully parallelizable in the horizontal and data structures are optimized for column-wise operation.

4.1.4 Experimental results

To measure the impact of our effort, we make the following configuration choices: 1) We disable the physics parametrizations in all configurations to be able to focus on the accelerated code region, the dynamical core. 2) We run the GPU-ported version with a single MPI task per allocated GPU, and the CPU version with one MPI task per available physical core. Tests have shown that using multiple processes per GPU results in slower code due to excessive context switching, OpenACC kernel launch overhead and too small chunks of work being

Figure 2: Strong scaling of the dynamical core for the alps case, simulated years per day as a function of number of deployed compute nodes.

No. nodes	No. grid cells per core	No. grid cells per GPU
1	297,143	3,565,719
2	148,571	1,782,859
4	74,286	891,430
8	37,143	445,714

Table 2: The number of grid cells (including the vertical direction) per CPU core and GPU card for the alps test case.

offloaded to the accelerators. This implies that unaffected code regions, such as initialization and physics parameterizations, are much slower for the GPU-accelerated runs because the CPU remains under-utilized.

The low-resolution med22 test case has predominantly been used to monitor the numerical equivalence of the OpenACC version and the CPU master branch. The former achieves parity with the gnu-compiled master branch in terms of performance when running on a single JUWELS-Booster node (i.e. 4 GPUs vs. 2x24 CPU cores). Beyond one node, the GPU version becomes slower than the CPU code (not depicted here).

For the alps test case (fig. 2), we have tested the GPU-ported performance on two systems: the previous-generation Marconi-100 machine at CINECA and the latest generation JUWELS-Booster partition at Juelich Supercomputing Center. The former has four Volta-generation GPUs per node, paired with a dual-socket IBM power9 architecture with 16 physical cores per socket. The latter combines 4 A100 cards with two 24-core AMD EPYC 7402 processors per node. For Marconi-100, we observe considerable speedup of the accelerated dycore (denoted acc-dycore:gpu), starting with a factor of 2 at a dual-node setup and which grows to almost a factor three for twelve nodes. The better scaling of the GPU code suggests that the communication overhead is preventing the CPU-version of RegCM to reach a good utilization of the CPUs on the machine. The picture is vastly different on JUWELS-Booster, where the RegCM master branch displays a much better scaling. We observe the OpenACC version to be significantly faster for a small number of nodes, starting at a factor 3 on a single node. Upon increasing the allocation, this speedup decreases to 25% at 4 nodes and eventually decreases after 6 nodes to a slowdown. In this regime, the chunk size of offloaded work (loops of typically 0.5M iterations, see table 2) is too small to efficiently utilize the A100 cards.

We also observe that the changes to the code to enhance parallelism have a substantial negative impact on the CPU performance; this penalty is small for lower core counts, but reduces the achievable simulation speed when less work is available per CPU core. We suspect that in this regime, the original cache-optimized code

Figure 3: nvprof timeline of a full time step of the alps test case running on 4x4 GPUs using OpenACC.

could efficiently make use of the L2 cache to store array slices for re-use. This mechanism was abandoned in the GPU port in favor of increased parallelism. To merge our effort into the main branch of RegCM, preprocessor directives have been inserted to execute the optimal code path depending on the programming model in use.

4.1.5 Perspectives

Looking at possible future activities regarding the RegCM acceleration, the scaling behavior of the non-hydrostatic dynamical core comes to mind. As pointed out previously, the program is very sensitive to communication overhead and focusing on single-threaded optimizations or GPU kernel optimization is not very useful until this bottleneck has been addressed. As can be seen from figure 3, the alps test case running on 16 GPUs spends most of its time waiting for data transfers, indicated by the white space in the timeline. Applying techniques like packing messages and overlapping communication with computation could benefit not only the OpenACC version of RegCM, but also the CPU code. A more drastic –but perhaps necessary– approach will be the inclusion of extensive halo regions throughout the advection sub-stepping, which will allow us to dismiss repeated halo exchanges during this split step and provides a pathway towards better scalability of the dycore. A simple experiment where we removed these halo exchanges within the `sound` and `wafone` routines resulted in another 100% speedup for the accelerated alps case on 4 nodes.

Finally, the acceleration of production runs with RegCM will depend on the degree to which physics parametrizations are ported to the GPU. We have ported the cloud microphysics scheme, and we note that the radiation scheme could be readily updated to a new version of RTE+RRTMGP that supports GPU offloading via OpenACC as well. Other code can be routinely equipped with device-offloading pragmas, or a source-to-source translation framework like LOKI (ref. needed) could be used.

4.1.6 Conclusion & Results

With the full non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM ported to GPUs using OpenACC, we have substantially increased the throughput and improved the scaling of RegCM on the Marconi100 supercomputer. Also on JUWELS Booster we observe promising speedups, albeit to a lesser degree due to the improved networking and compute capabilities of the processor architecture.

On JUWELS-Booster, the performance improvement decreases towards higher node counts, where realistic production-level climate simulations would benefit most. This is due to the fact that (i) the current GPU translation is predominantly a straightforward insertion of OpenACC directives with only a hand full of

optimizations at the source code level, and (ii) the abundant MPI communication within the dynamical core prevents the application from taking full advantage of the compute power of many interconnected GPU cards.

Looking forward, we identify three main routes towards better utilization of available compute resources. Firstly, the acceleration of the physics parameterizations will enable a speedup of realistic climate simulations involving radiation, clouds, convection and the surface scheme. This might also result in e.g. more frequent calls to the radiative transfer code to improve model accuracy. Secondly, an optimization of the loops and data layout and possibly tuning of the OpenACC kernels can greatly improve performance of the GPU-resident dynamical core. Finally, an optimization of the MPI communication within the advection substepping will benefit RegCM on both clusters as well as traditional higher-tier HPC systems.

4.2 MicroHH Service 1 project

MicroHH (van Heerwaarden et al., 2017) is an open-source computational fluid dynamics code for direct numerical simulation (DNS) and large-eddy simulation (LES) of atmospheric turbulent flows. Compared to current numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, LES does not rely on physical parameterisations for turbulence and clouds. Instead, it explicitly resolves the largest turbulent eddies by using a fine horizontal resolution of $\mathcal{O}(1-100\text{ m})$. This can reduce the uncertainty related to e.g. clouds and precipitation, and hence improve the quality of weather forecasts. Over the last few years, MicroHH has been extended with various physics parameterisations necessary to simulate realistic weather. This includes the RTE-RRTMGP radiative transfer model (Pincus et al., 2019), a single moment ice microphysics scheme (Tomita, 2008), and an interactive land-surface model (Balsamo et al., 2009). As such, the model can now be used to explore the benefits and limitations of using LES for weather predictions.

MicroHH can run fully on both the CPU (C++) and GPU (CUDA-C++), but the GPU version currently has some limitations. The porting of CPU to GPU kernels was done in a somewhat naive way, replacing only the CPU for loops by CUDA thread based indexing, without further CUDA-specific code optimisations. Furthermore, the GPU version only supports the use of single GPUs.

The goal of this ESiWACE2 project was twofold. Firstly, the main aim was to optimise the existing GPU code using the Kernel Launcher (Heldens and van Werkhoven, 2022) and Kernel Tuner (van Werkhoven, 2019) codes developed by NLeSC. Secondly, this project has explored the possibility to extend MicroHH to a multi-GPU setup.

4.2.1 MicroHH overview

MicroHH was developed from scratch in (more or less) the last decade. The initial CPU code was designed with a few important requirements:

- **Modern:** The code is written in C++, and uses elements of object-oriented programming and template metaprogramming.
- **Fast:** Throughout the model, the code is optimised to maximise loop vectorisation. In addition, the entire code can switch, at compile time, between single and double precision floating point numbers.
- **Highly parallel:** The model core is designed to run efficiently on $>10\text{K}$ CPU cores, and has shown excellent strong (up to 8192 cores) and weak (up to 32,768 cores) scaling. MPI-IO is used to store 2D and 3D fields in order to minimise the number of output files.
- **Memory efficient:** To limit the number of MPI tasks in expensive experiments, the code was designed to be as memory efficient as possible.
- **Open source:** To aid reproducibility and transparency in research, the entire code¹ and documentation² are openly available.

¹<https://github.com/microhh/microhh>

²<https://microhh.readthedocs.io/>

Figure 4: Screenshot of a initial performance profile for MicroHH inside the NVIDIA Nsight Systems GUI.

Many of the CPU code requirements naturally led to (and simplified) the development of a GPU version. For example, porting the code from C++ to CUDA-C++ is relatively straightforward, the memory efficiency is required as GPUs have limited memory, and the support for single precision floating point calculations is beneficial both from the perspective of memory usage, and when using consumer GPUs with poor double precision performance.

In the GPU version, we have chosen to port all code from the main time loop to the GPU. This way, memory transfers between the host and GPU are only required during the computation of time-integrated statistics and/or I/O time steps. The initial port from CPU to GPU code was done in a “naive” way, where the CPU `for` loops are replaced by CUDA thread-based indexing, but the loop body is essentially unchanged. Only in very obvious operations, like e.g. reductions or transposes, we used shared memory optimisations.

In the latest version of MicroHH, all model options – including radiation, microphysics, and land-surface model – are available on the GPU. Except for the RTE-RRTMGP radiation code, which was optimized in a previous ESiWACE Service 1 project, the GPU version has recently not been optimized or tuned for the latest NVIDIA architectures.

4.2.2 Initial performance analysis

Initial performance analysis was carried out to evaluate the current performance of the application and to determine the most computationally expensive GPU kernels. A performance trace was created using NVIDIA Nsight Systems CLI of MicroHH, for a simulation with dry convection (`drycb11es` case, e.g. Schmidt and Schumann, 1989), using double precision floating-point accuracy, a grid of $512 \times 512 \times 512$, and the 5th order accurate advection scheme (Wicker and Skamarock, 2002). The application was executed on a NVIDIA A100 GPU, a GPU targeted at HPC applications and based on the Ampere architecture, the latest GPU architecture by NVIDIA.

Figure 4 shows a screenshot of the performance profile inside the NVIDIA Nsight Systems GUI. Table 3 lists the top ten most computationally-expensive GPU kernels together with the percentage of the total run-time spent on executing this kernel. The table shows that 34% of the total execution time is spent on four GPU kernels related to advection and roughly 32% of the time is spent on three GPU kernels related to diffusion.

Table 3: Percentage of run-time for GPUs kernels for initial performance analysis.

GPU kernel name	Stage	Percentage of run-time
<code>evisc_g</code>	Diffusion	15.0%
<code>diff_uvw_g</code>	Diffusion	11.3%
<code>advec_u_g</code>	Advection	8.7%
<code>advec_v_g</code>	Advection	8.7%
<code>advec_w_g</code>	Advection	8.7%
<code>advec_s_g</code>	Advection	7.9%
<code>calc_straing2_g</code>	Diffusion	6.1%

These seven GPU kernels together make up two thirds of the total execution time and will be the targets for performance optimizations. Note that `advec_s` performs advection for one scalar field. While `drycb1les` uses only a single scalar, realistic cases can use another 8 scalar fields when using complex microphysics, and/or another 10-20 for simulations with atmospheric chemistry.

4.2.3 Performance Improvements

The seven selected GPU kernels all follow a similar pattern: Each launches one thread per grid point and processes the data elements for that one point.

In GPU programming, work is performed by submitting a large number of threads to the GPU that execute in parallel. These threads are grouped in 3D *thread blocks* and the dimensions of these thread blocks have an important impact on performance. By default, MicroHH uses the same thread block size of $256 \times 1 \times 1$ for all kernels in the application. Through experimental evaluation, we found that performance can be improved by tuning the block size. However, we also found that the optimal block size varies and depends heavily on many factors, such as the specific GPU kernel, the grid size, the floating-point precision, and the GPU architecture. Using the same thread block size for all kernels thus will not yield optimal performance and the optimal block size must be tuned for each scenario.

For each kernel, one GPU thread is launched per grid point. We found that performance can be improved by processing multiple grid points per thread (e.g., 2, 4 or 8 grid points per thread), thus making the work per thread more coarse-grained. This performance increase can be attributed to better memory locality and reuse of data by threads. However, the optimal thread granularity, similar to the optimal block size, differs per kernels and is influenced by many factors.

Through the use of NVIDIA Nsight Compute CLI, we determined that many of the GPU kernels had their occupancy limited by excessive register usage. We were able to reduce register usage of the kernel through the use of CUDA's `__launch_bounds__` code directive that hints to the NVIDIA compiler the desired minimum number of resident thread blocks per streaming multiprocessor (SM). However, selecting the optimal number of blocks per SM is again a parameter that must be tuned individually for each kernel.

Several kernels have also been optimized by rewriting their mathematical equations to use less expensive operations. For instance, it was found that the advection kernels perform divisions by the variable `rhoref`. Division of floating-point numbers is computationally expensive and, on GPUs, division can be an order of magnitude more expensive than multiplication. By precomputing the reciprocal of `rhoref` once during initialization, this division could be converted into a multiplication. Another notable example is `evisc_g` where equations could be written in a different way as to remove 4 divisions and 2 `pow` calls per grid point.

To determine the optimal parameters for the seven kernels for different scenarios, we used *Kernel Tuner* (van Werkhoven, 2019). Kernel Tuner is a tool for testing, validating, and automatic tuning of CUDA kernels. Kernel Tuner supports many different search optimization algorithms and is capable of handling the large and discontinuous search spaces that are common in tuning GPU kernels. To integrate the tuning results of Kernel Tuner back into MicroHH, we used *Kernel Launcher* (Heldens and van Werkhoven, 2022). Kernel Launcher is a C++ library that dynamically selects the optimal configuration for each kernel, compiles the CUDA kernel at runtime, and launches it on the GPU. This solution is future-proof since the kernels can easily be re-tuned for future GPU architectures.

We also experimented with several performance optimizations that were ultimately found to provide no performance benefits. We mention these here for completeness.

- Kernel fusion of the three advection kernels into a single kernel `advec_uvw`. This was found to be detrimental to performance.
- Use of shared memory to reduce memory access overhead. This optimization provided no performance benefit, likely since modern NVIDIA GPU architectures (Ampere) have large L1 caches that utilize the same physical memory unit as shared memory.

- Use of CUDA intrinsic functions to control caching behavior for memory loads and stores. This had negligible impact on performance.
- Change memory layout of the grid by adding padding to improve memory coalescing on the GPU. This resulted in a small performance improvement (5–10%) at the cost of increased memory usage. However, it was decided that this optimization was too intrusive since changing the memory layout would require rewriting all kernels in the entire application to adjust the indexing into memory.

4.2.4 Experimental Results

To evaluate the performance of the optimized kernels, we consider the `drycb11es` usecase for two grid sizes: a small grid of $256 \times 256 \times 256$ and a larger grid of $512 \times 512 \times 512$. Additionally, we consider the kernels for both single precision (32 bit) and double precision (64 bit) floating-point accuracy. The GPU used is an NVIDIA Ampere A100 having 40 GB of memory.

Figure 5 shows the absolute run-time for seven kernels in these four scenarios. The ‘baseline’ is the performance of the original kernels. The figure shows that for each of the seven kernels, the optimizations result in a performance increase. However, the amount of increase is not constant across all kernels but depends on the scenario.

Figure 6 shows the relative speedup instead of absolute run-times. We observe that all kernels see a performance increase of at least 5% after optimizations. The performance improvements across all kernels are larger for single precision than for double precision accuracy. For instance, for a $512 \times 512 \times 512$ grid, the average improvement is 60% for single precision and 45% for double precision runs.

Most notable are the improvements for the kernels `diff_uvw` and `evisc`, where we seem up to almost 200% increase in performance. The `diff_uvw` kernel uses a large number of intermediate values, thus careful tuning of the block size and the register usage leads to a large performance improvement. The `evisc` kernel uses various expensive mathematical operations (division, square root, power function), some of which could be removed by rewriting the equations, resulting in a noticeable performance improvement for double precision runs.

Finally, we present the execution time for the complete application. These execution times include the time spent on the GPU, but also the time spent on auxiliary tasks such as reading inputs, writing results, calculating statistics, and transferring data between memories. Figure 7 shows performance for the `drycb11es` case after 5000 time iterations. The figure shows that the performance increase is significant. For example, for double precision, the total run-time goes from around 35 minutes to less than 30 minutes. The overall decrease in run-time is 14% for double precision and 17% for single precision.

4.2.5 Perspectives

To test the impact of the MicroHH optimizations on a realistic use case, we compared the performance of a single A100 GPU with the CPU version of MicroHH, for a simulation of realistic weather over the KNMI measurement tower near Cabauw, the Netherlands. The results in Fig. 8 show that ~ 400 - 430 CPU cores are needed to match the performance of a single GPU. As one A100 GPU costs 128 CPU hours/hour on the Snellius supercomputer, this means that moving simulations to the GPU reduces the computational costs with a factor ~ 3.2 - 3.4 . For simulations without radiative transfer – which is a process that is difficult to optimize on the GPU – the reduction in computational costs increases to a factor ~ 7.5 (not shown).

Reducing the computational costs with a factor ~ 3 - 3.5 is a large step forward towards (1) the routine use of realistic LES – including e.g. radiative transfer and microphysics – in research, and (2) exploring the use of LES in weather forecasting. In addition, the decrease in computational costs directly increases the potential of ongoing research in a number of national projects, like e.g. the Ruisdael Observatory³, and European Horizon

³<https://ruisdael-observatory.nl/>

Figure 5: Performance of optimized kernels versus baseline in milliseconds.

Figure 6: Speedup of optimized kernels over baseline.

Figure 7: Run-time in minutes of full application for 5000 time iterations.

Figure 8: MicroHH performance on CPU and GPU (40 GB A100 on the Snellius supercomputer).

2020 projects like MEMO2⁴ and CoCO2⁵.

4.2.6 Conclusion & Results

ESiWACE2 made important contributions to the optimization of the GPU version of MicroHH, but also created a solid infrastructure for the optimization of future additions to the model. Combined with the Kernel Launcher and Kernel Tuner, this should make MicroHH future-proof and a competitive GPU-capable LES model.

The majority of supercomputers nowadays rely on GPUs to provide high performance. For instance, the Frontier system⁶, the first operational exascale system in the world, is capable of delivering its massive performance solely thanks to its 37,888 GPUs. Optimizing and tuning the performance of scientific applications for GPUs is thus important in moving towards exascale. With this work, we have brought MicroHH one step closer to the exascale era.

4.3 Summary of work in WP3: HPC Services

The work in Work Package 3 consists of three services and its coordination. Service 1 and Service 2 have worked with open calls for proposals to create collaborative projects. Service 3 did not use any calls for proposals mechanism, but directly contributed to advance the development of the HPCW benchmark suite.

⁴<https://h2020-memo2.eu/>

⁵<https://coco2-project.eu>

⁶<https://www.top500.org/system/180047/>

Because separate deliverables (D3.2, D3.3, and D3.4) already reported the work performed in Service 1, 2, and 3, respectively, we only provide a brief overview here.

4.3.1 Service 1: code portability and refactoring

An overview of the projects created in Service 1 is presented in Table 4. All projects except FESOM2 and DALES received 6 person months of guidance, advice, and engineering support by the Research Software Engineers of the Netherlands eScience Center and Atos. The projects on FESOM2 and DALES were initially granted as 6 person month projects in 2020, but both projects re-applied for another 6-month project in 2021, respectively. The table lists projects in chronological order. The "target HW" column lists the supercomputing systems that were targeted by the model developing groups and RSEs during the service project and mainly include European supercomputers.

It is interesting to note that out of 10 projects in total, four projects mainly focused on improving existing parallelization and communication for MPI-based CPU applications, 3 applied for assistance in porting codes to the GPU where there was no existing GPU code already, and 3 projects were about optimizing existing GPU implementations. While this is a small sample of projects, it may suggest at least that optimizing existing GPU code is as difficult as porting code to GPUs in the first place.

Name	Type	Service goal	Target HW	Existing GPU code
FESOM2	Ocean sea ice model	Port tracer transport to GPUs	JUWELS-Booster	No
DALES	Atmospheric turbulence and cloud physics	Improve communication, integrate libraries, explore mixed-precision	Cartesius, Snellius & Fugaku	No
EMAC	Atmospheric chemistry	Optimize GPU implementation	JUWELS-Booster & BullSequana XH2000	Yes
OBLIMAP2	Climate-ice sheet model coupling code	Improve parallelization	BullSequana XH2000	No
AGRIF	Adaptive grid ocean modeling	Optimize communication	BullSequana XH2000	No
RTE+RRTMGP	Radiative transfer model	Optimize GPU implementation	Snellius supercomputer	Yes
BLOM	Ocean model	Optimize MPI+OpenMP implementation	Betzy supercomputer	No
OGSTM	Marine biogeochemistry	Port tracer transport to GPUs	Marconi100 & Leonardo	No
RegCM	Regional Climate	Blueprint to port to GPUs	Marconi100 & JUWELS-Booster	No
MicroHH	Atmospheric turbulence	Optimize GPU implementation	Snellius supercomputer	Yes

Table 4: Overview of the Service projects in Service 1.

4.3.2 Service 2: Coupling, IO and workflows

Service 2 differs from Service 1 in several ways. Service 2 targets users of weather and climate models, as opposed to targeting only model developing groups. The projects in Service 2 are significantly shorter, one to three person months. And projects in Service 2 are focused on optimizing or enhancing the application of any of three supported community-developed tools that are widely used in the weather and climate research communities. These tools are OASIS3-MCT, a model coupling toolkit, XIOS, a library dedicated to I/O management in climate codes, and Cylc, a general purpose workflow engine typically used in weather, climate, and environmental forecasting. The service projects in Service 2 are a great opportunity for end users to receive direct guidance and support in the application of a tool to a specific use case by the team originally developing that specific tool. For the tool-developing groups that deliver the service projects, there is also a mutual benefit of directly receiving feedback on the end user experience by real users of the tool during the project.

An overview of the service projects provided in Service 2 is given in Table 5. From this overview, it is clear that widely-used European models such as NEMO or the UM are the typical targets for the advanced end user support provided in Service 2.

Institute	Tool	Target software	Type	Service goal
NERSC	OASIS	NEMO	Ocean modelling	Online calculation of interpolation weights
Met Office	OASIS	UKESM	Earth System Modelling	Degraded resolution coupling
Met Office	XIOS	LFRic	Atmospheric model	Optimize use of XIOS for writing output files
Mercator Ocean	XIOS	NEMO	Ocean modelling	Scalability of atmospheric forcing in NEMO
ICM Poland	Cylc	Various, including WAM, UM, WRF, GFS	Weather and climate	Design and optimisation of the general workflow for ICM coupled model
NCAS-CMS	Cylc	Various, including UM	Weather and climate	Migration to Cylc 8 and Archer 2

Table 5: Overview of the Service projects in Service 2.

4.3.3 Service 3: Weather and climate benchmarking

ESiWACE2 took over the HPCW benchmark suite when the ESCAPE2 project ended. As part of Service 3, ESiWACE2 has extended the HPCW suite to represent a wider range of weather and climate models, and has tested the performance of the HPCW benchmarks on different computing systems, including the pre-exascale supercomputers funded by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking.

Benchmarks that have been added are dwarf-p-cloudsc and ecTrans. The dwarf-p-cloudsc code is a benchmark application for the ECMWF cloud microphysics parameterization of the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). This includes several GPU-enabled versions of the CLOUDSC mini-app that use OpenACC directives to offload computational kernels to the GPU, with various levels of GPU-specific code optimizations. ecTrans is a global spherical Harmonics transforms library, also extracted from the IFS. ecTrans is using a hybrid of MPI and OpenMP parallelisation strategies.

Another important aspect of the work on HPCW is related to maintenance to ensure HPCW can be used

on current and future European (pre-)exascale supercomputers. As such, several dependencies and models that are used within the HPCW benchmarks have been updated. To simplify the process of building and deploying HPCW on new systems, recipes have been created to build the HPCW components using SPACK, a package manager that currently sees widespread use among HPC systems.

4.4 Lessons learned from the service projects

We have gathered the lessons learned from the research software engineers who worked on the services, and grouped them into six themes: Computer and Software Architectures, Software Testing, Programming Languages and Models, Enhancing Performance, Software Sustainability, and the lessons learned that are specific to Service Projects.

4.4.1 Computer and Software Architectures

Computer architectures have become more and more complex and heterogeneous in the past decades, and there are clear indications that the trend of increasing specialization in computing hardware is to continue in at least the next two decades. However, it is almost certain that some form of (GPU-like) accelerator will be involved. And while these architectures evolve, and predicting their evolution becomes challenging, software still needs to adapt. As such, software architecture is of the utmost importance, because porting badly organized code to new architectures can become an insurmountable task.

Software architecture is considered an important topic by most weather and climate model developing groups. However, it is important to realize that large modelling codes may see periods of active development spread across several decades, for example, development of ecTrans (part of the HPCW Benchmark suite in Service 3) dates back to 1987. While software is typically considered to be easier to change than hardware, reorganizing, let alone rewriting hundreds of thousands of lines of source code is far from an easy task.

The transition to exascale systems presents a number of challenges that specifically impact the software architecture of weather and climate models. After a long period of market dominance by Nvidia, the first generation of exascale systems shows increased diversity in terms of hardware vendors, with systems using also AMD or Intel GPUs. As such, it is important to isolate computational kernels as much as possible from the rest of the software, to allow these to be easily replaced by different implementations for different hardware backends. Another impacting design choice is the increase in the number of GPUs per node, from typically two or four to now six or even eight. This change has a lot of impact on the overall application, as it changes the balance between MPI-tasks and GPU-tasks, impacts GPU memory management, as well as communication patterns. As a consequence, the total fraction of compute power offered by the CPUs in the system is diminishing. This can be important for weather and climate models as it may severely impact parts of the models typically not ported to GPUs, such as I/O and the computation of time-integrated statistics.

4.4.2 Software Testing

Weather and climate models are generally validated to ensure the predictions and long-term climate patterns that emerge from simulations have statistical significance. The validation process of climate models is a specialized and scientific exercise and requires a number of test cases and large runs, possibly using multiple ensemble runs. The validation effort is, however important, in large part unrelated to software testing. Software tests are usually, but not always, present in the source codes of weather and climate models and serve to signal bugs or other issues with model at the level of the source code.

The importance of tests is exacerbated when porting models to different architectures, because the differences caused by new hardware, compilers, libraries, and programming languages tend to trigger new bugs that are difficult to catch without available tests. Developers should use reliable and preferably automatic ways to check numerical results, or even better integrate tests within their software. This approach is far less

error prone than having humans comparing images with their naked eyes, and allows for a more streamlined development process.

4.4.3 Programming Languages and Models

In recent years, we have moved from a world in which developers could choose between C or Fortran depending on their knowledge or working environment, to a world in which every vendor has a different programming language. For programming GPUs, there are many different options. CUDA, OpenCL, and more recently HIP and SYCL are specialized GPU programming languages for writing computational kernels that execute data-parallel workloads on the GPU. Directive-based approaches, such as OpenACC and OpenMP, allow the code to remain in its original programming language and may be used to instruct the compiler to generate GPU kernels for specific parts of the code. Recently, language standard parallelism has been introduced in C++ and Fortran to allow the developer to indicate parallelism directly from the original programming language.

Weather and climate models are usually the result of many years of research and development work, and usually have grown into a code base that is large and complex. Due to investments in optimization and scalability, their performance landscape is often flat, lacking key computational bottlenecks. Accelerating such applications typically requires porting substantial blocks of code to the GPU. Here we see that directive-based programming models like OpenACC and OpenMP have leverage, also from a software sustainability perspective.

However, such programming models have their limitations: sometimes loops are not optimized for parallelism but for e.g. cache use on the CPU. This can result in very poor GPU performance and requires separate versions of a certain block of code for specific hardware targets. Maintaining multiple versions of the code puts a burden on the maintainers, and actually cancels out one of the main motivations behind the choice for a directive-based programming model.

The issue of changing data layouts is more general and does not only affect directive-based programming models. In the case of OGSTM, we have seen that extracting parallelism actually degraded the overall performance of the model because the original data layout of a submodel, called BFM, was suboptimal, but the issue was even more visible with increased parallelism. Changing the data layout in a weather and climate model often has a profound impact on the source code that requires changes in nearly every part of the source code. Maintaining multiple competing data layout schemes in a single code base is often not feasible for small development teams with project-based budgets.

Language native parallel constructs give perhaps a cleaner entry point into parallel execution for applications developers, removing the issue of having to maintain multiple implementations of the same code base, and recently, GPU compilers are starting to support language standard parallelism in Fortran and C++, allowing for an easy offload to these accelerators. However, it should be noted that language standard parallelism will only offer high-level access to accelerators and therefore, much like directive-based approaches, cannot be used to implement highly-optimized codes that use the hardware to the fullest of its capabilities.

4.4.4 Enhancing Performance

Based on the work performed in the services, we see three distinct, but not orthogonal, avenues to improving the performance of weather and climate models: improving the scalability of the code, using mixed-precision, and optimizing the code to fully exploit the underlying hardware.

Scalability Although weather and climate models often have invested significant effort in optimizing the parallel scaling of the application, increasing the available resources and target resolution may reveal yet unnoticed scaling issues. One such case is the OGSTM project, where the naive domain decomposition of the regular ocean grid would introduce workload imbalances across MPI tasks due to the uneven distribution of land cells. Developing more advanced domain decomposition strategies and workload distribution schemes

may be beyond the capability or interest of the model developers, but essential to achieve a good utilization of the available hardware.

The inherent parallel nature of the weather and climate grid-based models also gives a new dimension to the GPU porting work; applications can only benefit from the GPU if (i) enough work can be offloaded to the device and (ii) the model does not suffer from MPI communication bottlenecks. By accelerating the throughput per MPI task via GPU offloading may therefore give rise to new, unforeseen scalability bottlenecks that were previously hidden in the performance profile. On the other hand, for many models the increased per-node compute power presents an opportunity to tune the per-node workloads and postpone MPI scalability issues that would arise when using many compute nodes.

Mixed-precision It is important to realize that the use of double precision floating-point numbers is rarely needed in weather and climate models; usually, model errors and uncertainty in the initial state are much larger than round-off errors and typically, the numerics where double-precision operations are required (for e.g. convergence or large cancellations) are only needed in a few places in the code. Lowering the precision of the model state variables can greatly increase the achieved throughput because the limited memory bandwidth can accommodate more array transfers. Another advantage of reduced precision models is that the model state uses less memory, which typically helps on systems like *Fugaku*, where nodes are equipped with limited-capacity high-bandwidth memory. Also for GPU-based systems, being able to fit more gridpoints per device and do computations in single precision increases the performance tremendously.

Code optimization GPU architectures are becoming increasingly complex, making it increasingly challenging to program these devices and exploit their computational power to the fullest potential. There are many optimizations that may improve performance in some cases, but might be detrimental to performance in other cases. For example, GPU have different levels of memory (e.g., texture memory, shared memory, constant memory) and the decision on what data to place at what level impacts performance. Other examples of these optimizations are loop unrolling, spatial blocking, utilizing warp functions, prefetching, and vectorization. Hijma et al. (2022) provide an extensive overview of such optimizations by analyzing 450 publications on GPU optimizations from the last 14 years.

Often when programming GPUs, there are many trade-offs that need to be made that have an important impact on performance. All in all, GPU programmers must tune their code to find the right balance between trade-offs to achieve optimal performance. However, this optimum is not fixed for each GPU kernel since it also depends on the workload (i.e., dataset size and precision) and the hardware platform. Some optimizations that work well for one type of GPU or one workload, might not work well for another GPU architecture or a smaller/large dataset.

This means that GPU programmers must not only tune their GPU kernels, but also tune them for each possible combination of GPU type and workload. This makes manual tuning by hand a time-consuming and challenging task. Fortunately, there also exist *auto-tuning tools* that can automatically find the optimum configuration for GPU kernels for each combination of workload and GPU type. As part of the ESiWACE2 Service 1 projects, we have used such an auto-tuning tool, *Kernel Tuner* (van Werkhoven, 2019), and we expect that auto-tuning tools will become fundamental to achieving high performance for GPU applications in the coming years.

4.4.5 Software Sustainability

Software sustainability is commonly defined as "the capacity to endure and preserve the function of a system over an extended period of time." Lago et al. (2015). In the context of porting weather and climate models to new architectures such as GPUs, there are many aspects concerning software sustainability.

The most profound aspect being that any code that is translated to a different programming language needs to be understood and maintained by the original developer team after the porting effort has completed.

Similarly, if the porting effort has resulted in multiple versions of the code, whether it is because a second version co-exists in a GPU programming language, or the GPU port in itself required fundamental changes to the CPU code, all these versions now need to be in scope for future maintenance.

Because of this need to maintain the code for the foreseeable future, weather and climate model developers may not want to depend on programming languages, libraries, or tools that they are not well versed in, have no control over, or that are still in experimental/research stage and may themselves not be properly maintained in the future.

To ensure that the effort invested in porting weather and climate code to new architectures is continued and further improved in the future, it is essential for the original model developers to have the skills to test and extend upon the work from the beginning of the project. This means it may be required for them to follow trainings in the technology that is used to port the code, such as, for example OpenACC.

4.4.6 Service Projects

In general, six months of development time is an appropriate time scale to achieve a speedup of the code and a clear picture of potential next steps for the software. However, it is too short to investigate more intrusive changes that actually might give a leap in performance, such as reordering data layouts. Such refactoring should be done either in a simplified mini-app application as a research project, or with a larger budget.

Working with two separate institutes on the same software with Corona restrictions has proven to be a challenge, and as a consequence, the division of work has converged towards a more homogeneous, single responsibility process. However, having multiple experts attend the online meetings with the model developers has proven to be very valuable and the fresh view of consortium colleagues has led to new insights and approaches on multiple occasions.

Choosing which section of the model to accelerate is a key aspect to get right. Often applicants have already a section in mind, but in our experience the decision can only be made after careful code inspection and profiling of a typical use case, on both a production-level node allocation as well as a smaller allocation that highlights the bottlenecks in memory bandwidth and compute. Moreover, one should consider potential future efforts and opportunities to maximize the impact of the work. As an example, we have chosen to accelerate tracer transport in FESOM2 because future couplings to ocean biochemistry will likely multiply the footprint of this section. In RegCM, we have chosen the dynamical core to highlight the potential of GPU computing for the application.

When a model relies heavily on an external component (e.g. OGSTM relies on BFM) that may or may not be maintained by the model developers, it is important to ensure beforehand that we have control over said component (to optimize it, tune it, or perhaps alter its API) as it could become a serious bottleneck in the target model otherwise.

4.5 Bottlenecks on the road to exascale

In the broad and diverse European ecosystem of weather and climate models, many computer codes are maintained by a small team of scientists; their primary focus is on finding more accurate numerical schemes and physical processes rather than optimizing the code for new hardware architecture. Nevertheless, they recognize that optimization is a necessary task: being able to drive the model towards higher resolutions and bigger ensembles are key in the pursuit of more accurate climate simulations and weather forecasts. Unfortunately, these small research groups are not able to benefit from the heterogeneous architectures that rule current European pre-exascale systems and (likely) upcoming exascale machines. There is no time and budget to port applications to GPU architectures, and even if there is, the expertise to make future-proof decisions is absent in many research groups.

The uncertainty about which programming model to adopt, what kind of data structures to choose and how fine-grained parallelism should be exposed prevents modelling groups from transforming their applications

into performance-portable, high-quality software. Navigating through the landscape of compilers, programming models, domain-specific languages and hardware architectures has become much more tedious with the advent of accelerators providing the bulk of compute capacity of large supercomputers. Unbiased advice and expert guidance is paramount and badly needed within the modelling community. There is a serious risk of apathy among the scientific programmers working on these codes, a tendency to believe that heterogeneous architectures are a trend that will pass eventually, or device offloading will become a standard and automated compiler feature.

Another aspect of complexity that arises in the era of heterogeneous architectures is that of performance tuning. As GPU computing rapidly evolves, the optimal parallel layout for a given algorithm or loop can wildly vary between generations and vendors of GPU cards. The compiler is generally not capable of generating the most efficient division of work and blocks of threads combination from heuristic inspection of the loop body – for low-level programming models like CUDA, the compiler isn't even supposed to make such a choice. Hence one may introduce tuning parameters inside the model code, which obfuscates the control flow and underlying algorithm. Moreover, for large weather and climate model code bases the number of such parameters may grow indefinitely and a clear strategy to find the optimal values is nonexistent at the application level.

Finally, the biggest obstruction towards exascale is the fundamental problem of weather and climate models being predominantly memory-bandwidth bound problems. Although modern GPU cards have enormous memory bandwidth compared to general-purpose processors, their ratio memory bandwidth over compute capacity has steadily decreased with each new generation. This means that traditional weather and climate models –even when fully ported to accelerators– can only utilize a tiny fraction of the advertised peak compute capability.

4.6 Addressing exascale challenges

Firstly, awareness among modelling centers must be increased: it should be stressed that heterogeneous architectures will become predominant within the European supercomputing ecosystem in the near future; to make use of the bulk compute capability means applications need to adopt a programming model that supports offloading to accelerators. This fact is widely known and accepted throughout the large weather centers and climate modelling groups, but the message has yet to come across to the wider geosciences community. The message should not be brought as a warning or commandment, but rather an opportunity to increase the fidelity and resolution of the next generation weather and climate models.

Secondly, the knowledge gap experienced by European modelling groups can effectively be mitigated by proper support and training from external partners, who possess the expertise and experience to advance applications towards more effective hardware utilization. This support may come from national institutes and programs, or European collaborations such as the ESiWACE2 services. A potential advantage of the latter is the ability to tap into the expertise of 'lighthouse' application developers and a higher degree of specialization. These experts can provide valuable input to the modelling groups regarding the question of adopting a programming model, and throughout the development process, it is useful to receive recommendations on code optimization and potential pitfalls. For this model to work smoothly, access to accelerator-based pre-exascale machines is crucial, and support from local supercomputing center staff preferable.

Thirdly, performance portability must be addressed. Performance portability refers to the ability of an application to execute efficiently across problems and different platforms. In the context of exascale supercomputers this includes executing efficiently on GPUs from different vendors, which is extremely challenging. We believe there is a need for software development tools that can aide weather and climate model developers to create performance portable applications. For example:

- Tools that work with existing code and in the language used by model developers are easier to adopt. As such, directive-based approaches are rightfully popular among weather and climate model developers. While many models are currently using OpenACC, there are concerns about portability of OpenACC code to GPUs from vendors other than Nvidia. In the FESOM2 Service project, we have used FYPP

macros to write performance portable loops that can execute efficiently on the CPU, as well as the GPU using OpenACC directives. This use of FYPP also paves the way for an OpenMP port of FESOM2 with even increased performance portability.

- Domain-specific languages (DSLs) provide a separation of concerns between the description of the algorithm and its implementation on specific hardware. DSLs provide a perfect platform to create performance portable applications from the perspective of the application developer, as the responsibility to come up with efficient implementations on each and every platform is now shifted towards the DSL developers. A downside to the DSL approach is that many DSLs require the application to be rewritten entirely in the language of the DSL. Given the size of most weather and climate codebases, porting a code to the DSL is a considerable effort that not all model developers want to make, since it requires a great deal of confidence in the DSL developers and trust that the DSL will see continued development over the next decades. Not all DSLs suffer from this problem, for example PSyClone, developed in ESiWACE2 Work Package 2, allows Fortran applications to gradually migrate functions to the DSL.
- Tools to help create highly-efficient performance portable applications. Auto-tuning can be used to achieve high performance on various platforms and is therefore often regarded as a technique to achieve performance portability. However, a fundamental problem is that auto-tuning results are highly dependent not only on the application, but also on the aspects such as the hardware platform and the dataset size or precision. As such, tools should either tune the code at runtime or select the optimal implementation for the current problem at hand. *Kernel Launcher* (Heldens and van Werkhoven, 2022) is currently being developed to this end.

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6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

One of the primary difficulties encountered during the ESiWACE2 Services was the Covid-19 pandemic. Originally, every service project was planned to include at least one multi-day visit by the research software engineers to the group developing the weather or climate model. However, during the pandemic travel was no longer possible and we all soon discovered that the service projects could be executed successfully in a fully remote fashion. As such, we removed the site visits from the call for proposals of the service 1 projects running in 2021 and 2022.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The development of European High Performance Computing (HPC) is based on a European Commission strategy paper from 2012, which stipulates the operation of three pillars: HPC Research Infrastructure, HPC Technology, and HPC Application Expertise. The HPC Research Infrastructure is represented by PRACE, a network of supercomputers that is available for scientific research projects based on a peer review process. The HPC Technology pillar is represented by ETP4HPC, an industry-led association that aims to build a globally competitive HPC technology industry in Europe. Its main deliverable is the European HPC Strategic Research Agenda, which defines the priorities for research and development in HPC technology. The HPC Application Expertise pillar is developed through the Centres of Excellence in Computing Applications (CoEs), which are tasked with developing, maintaining, and enhancing HPC applications in various domains. ESiWACE2 is a Centre of Excellence in the HPC Application Expertise pillar. The ESiWACE2 Services represent the largest effort within the ESiWACE2 project to directly engage with the wider community, outside of the ESiWACE2 consortium partners, of weather and climate model developers to provide advice, guidance and engineering to develop and enhance the performance of weather and climate applications for pre-exascale systems.

Since the first call for proposals for ESiWACE2 Service 1 projects, we have encouraged proposals to target accelerator hardware such as GPUs, expecting that these will constitute the bulk of the capability of future exascale systems. In these projects, we have helped to port the critical path of the code to the accelerator and tune the resulting code for maximal compute performance on the device. We also encouraged proposals to apply for projects in which we would port the code to GPUs using any of the domain-specific languages (DSLs) developed in other work packages of ESiWACE2, but have not received such proposals. As such, we have mainly used OpenACC and in some cases CUDA to port code to the GPU. Now that the ESiWACE2 project is in its final stages, we can see that GPUs have indeed become the mainstream platform for HPC systems in Europe. Seven out of eight systems funded through the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking in 2021 and 2022 are using Graphics Processing Units as their main computing platform.

However, most of these systems are expected to be operational for 5 to 7 years. It is important to realize that HPC applications, and in particular weather and climate simulating codes, generally have much longer lifetimes. It is therefore crucial to ensure that the software can be easily ported to new computing

architectures. In Service 1, we have collaborated with model developing groups to help them organize their code in a way that simplifies the current and future porting efforts. Through the use of advanced software development tools, such as using auto-tuning and run-time kernel selection, we have created performance portable codes that are able to extract full performance of the underlying hardware without the need to hard-code any architecture specific optimizations.

Over time, usage practices of weather and climate codes have evolved towards more complex scenarios. For example, existing models are now being used as component models in coupled simulations or as part of larger Earth System simulations, or by incorporating real-world observations into the model using data assimilation, existing models are used to create accurate forecasts and predictions of weather and climate patterns. Service 2 has helped to optimize the use of workflows, coupling, and IO tools to enable use of existing models in such complex scenarios. Whereas Service 3 has advanced the state of the HPCW benchmark suite to allow the community to enable co-design and evaluate the capabilities of new supercomputing systems to efficiently execute such weather and climate workloads.

8 Sustainability

The ESiWACE2 Services, and in particular Service 1, have served as a blueprint for the services defined in the follow-up project ESiWACE3. ESiWACE3 is funded by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking and is in many ways a successor of ESiWACE2. The ESiWACE3 project will start in January 2023. The ESiWACE3 Services (Work Package 4) will have a number of procedures built-in to ensure a sustainable impact on the software landscape of European weather and climate models.

It is important to understand that these procedures will come in addition to the practices that we currently have in place for services in ESiWACE2. First of all, as part of the application procedure the lead applicant currently has to supply (among others): the purpose of the software, scientific relevance, goal of the collaboration, and a timeline. A subset of the information that we request as part of the application is specifically focused on sustainability, including:

- What governance structure do you have in place for your software? (who decides what functionality ends up in final released versions of the software)
- If the software is released under any license(s), what are they?
- Who is currently involved in developing the software? Please also mention any external partners
- Please provide access information to the source code repository of the software (e.g. a git repository of the code). The code will be inspected as part of the technical review of the proposal.
- How would the proposed project benefit you, your software, and the research community? Where possible, specify any research groups, projects, companies or other teams or individuals that would directly benefit from this proposed work, and how they would benefit.
- Please indicate how many developers from your lab or institute will be actively involved for the duration of the collaboration.

Furthermore, the proposals are reviewed in two phases. First, a technical feasibility and software sustainability check is performed by the RSEs of the Netherlands eScience Center and ATOS. The technical review decides which proposals make it to round 2, the scientific review. In the second round, the grant decision is made by the scientific review committee, which consists of established researchers in the weather and climate community, both internal and external to the ESiWACE consortium. The scientific review committee assesses the scientific relevance and impact of the work.

In addition, to the practices and procedures in place for ESiWACE2, we will implement the following in ESiWACE3 to ensure sustainable, long-lasting impact of our work:

- The nature of work by the RSEs in the services will focus more on providing guidance and advice and less on the RSEs doing engineering in isolation. The goal of the collaboration is to port the software to new hardware platforms in such a way that the current team of developers of the software will also be able to perform maintenance on the software after the project has ended. As such, more time will be spent on education and training in order to transfer the technical skills of the RSEs.
- Every year that we have running service projects, we will end that year with a workshop that focuses on sharing lessons learned and disseminating the achieved results to the weather and climate community.
- We will include a Software Management Plan (SMP) as part of the application form that explicitly requires the lead applicants to consider software sustainability as a key factor in the project. The software sustainability plan must include (among others) the following information: Software license, publicly accessible version control repository, FORCE11 recommendations for software citation, use of DOI, inclusion in a relevant directory for research software, documentation targeting new users, plans for the software's longevity, an overview of the current user community of the software
- We will implement a structured evaluation procedure for service projects. In ESiWACE2, we held surveys each year after projects had finished to request feedback on the quality, impact, and relevance of the services. Participation in the survey is encouraged, but is ultimately voluntary. In ESiWACE3, we take an even more structured evaluation approach by organizing an individual project end interview with the lead applicant of each service project. In addition, as was introduced for the last year of ESiWACE2, we will require a written report by the lead applicant, which details the progress that has been made and impact of the work.

Finally, the current state and potential impact of the ESiWACE3 Services on the European community of weather and climate model developing groups will be assessed at the start of the project. In the first nine months of the project, a screening task will create an overview of all weather and climate models that are currently being developed in Europe and their readiness for modern computing platforms, such as parallel computers and GPUs.

9 Dissemination, engagement and uptake of results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We ensure the uptake of the deliverable by the targeted audience through the following actions

This deliverable will be publicly made available on the ESiWACE Zenodo repository. The results will be presented at scientific conferences, such as the European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly and/or International Supercomputing Conference (ISC-HPC). A conference paper about the lessons learned from the ESiWACE2 services is currently in preparation for a scientific conference in High Performance Computing and/or Research Software Engineering. A conference paper about the application of new auto-tuning technologies Kernel Launcher in MicroHH is currently in preparation for a computer science conference in software optimization and performance tuning.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

The work performed within each of the ESiWACE2 services has been covered in separate deliverables; Service 1 in D3.2, Service 2 in D3.3, Service 3 in D3.4. As such, many of the dissemination and engagement activities have been listed in the deliverable specific to that service. Table 6 only lists the dissemination and engagement activities that had not yet happened or were not yet listed in the service-specific deliverables.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

The work performed within each of the ESiWACE2 services has been covered in separate deliverables; Service 1 in D3.2, Service 2 in D3.3, Service 3 in D3.4. As such, most publications have been listed in the deliverable specific to that service. Table 7 only lists the publications that were not listed in any of the service-specific deliverables.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

No intellectual property right resulted from this deliverable.

Table 6: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	Ben van Werkhoven - Generic Autotuning Technology for GPU Applications - Lorentz Center Workshop	March 7 - 11, 2022, Lorentz Center, Oort building, Leiden, the Netherlands	Scientific Community	https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/generic-autotuning-technology-for-gpu-applications.html	30
Participation to a conference	Chiel van Heerwaarden - (Auto)-tuning of the RTE+RRTMGP radiation model to speed up weather and climate models, Invited talk	March 10, 2022, Lorentz Center, Leiden, the Netherlands	Scientific Community	n/a	30
Organisation of a workshop	Alessio Sciocco, Ben van Werkhoven, Henk Dreuning, Stijn Heldens - GPU code optimization and auto-tuning made easy with Kernel Tuner: a hands-on, bring your own code tutorial, ISC-HPC 2022	May 29, 2022, Hamburg, Germany	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669255	10
Training	Ben van Werkhoven, Alessio Sciocco, "Kernel Tuner tutorial at SURF HPC/ML group"	November 7, 2022, SURF, Amsterdam, the Netherlands	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669273	20
Training	Ben van Werkhoven, Alessio Sciocco, "Porting of Codes for Next Generation GPU Architectures"	December 16, 2022 (online)	Scientific Community	https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/1466/	20

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Training	Ben van Werkhoven, Alessio Sciocco, "A24 - A Programmer's Guide for Modern High-Performance Computing"	December 14, 2022, Hoeven, the Netherlands	Scientific Community	https://asci.tudelft.nl/project/a24-a-programmers-guide-for-modern-high-performance-computing/	30
Training	Ben van Werkhoven, Alessio Sciocco, "HPC UvA GPU Programming Course"	January 26, 2023, Amsterdam, the Netherlands	Computer Science master students	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669373	40
Participation to a conference	Ben van Werkhoven, "Automatically Exploring GPU Design Spaces for Increased Productivity and Sustainability", Invited talk, SIAM Conference on Computational Science and Engineering (CSE23)	March 1, 2023, Amsterdam, the Netherlands	Scientific Community	n/a	Unknown

Table 7: Publications related to this deliverable

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Published	A Case Study of Cumulus Convection Over Land in Cloud-Resolving Simulations With a Coupled Ray Tracer	Menno Veerman, Bart van Stratum, and Chiel van Heerwaarden	Geophysical Research Letters	yes
Published	litstudy: A Python package for literature reviews	S. Heldens, A. Sclocco, H. Drenning, B. van Werkhoven, P. Hijma, J. Maassen, R. V. van Nieuwpoort	SoftwareX 2022	yes
In preparation	Acceleration of the non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM using GPUs	Alessio Sclocco, Gijs van den Oord, Graziano Giuliani, Ivan Girotto, Erwan Raffin, Ben van Werkhoven	EGU General Assembly 2023	yes
In preparation	Kernel Launcher: Automatic Run-time Kernel Selection for Auto-Tuned GPU Applications	Stijn Heldens and Ben van Werkhoven	The International Workshop on Automatic Performance Tuning (IWAPT 2023) held in conjunction with IPDPS 2023	Yes
In preparation	Lessons learned in the ESiWACE2 Services: preparing the weather and climate community for exascale supercomputers	Ben van Werkhoven, Gijs van den Oord, Alessio Sclocco, Stijn Heldens, Victor Azizi, David Guibert, Loris Lucido, Georges-Emmanuel Moulard, Erwan Raffin	to be decided	Yes